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An expression screen to identify genes important for trastuzumab resistance: Mica-as1.

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We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in patients sensitive or resistant to treatment with trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer for discovery of genes that confer or support resistance to HER2-targeted therapies in humans. In this manuscript we describe identification of Mica-as1 as a candidate gene product of the trastuzumab resistance gene expression signature.

Citations

1. Choy, M.K. and Phipps, M.E., 2010. MICA polymorphism: biology and importance in immunity and disease. Trends in molecular medicine, 16(3), pp.97-106.